

ROADS AND CITIES: THE TASHKENT OASIS IN THE MIDDLE AGES

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Abstract: The article examines the communication system of the Tashkent oasis, including its caravan routes, the development of urbanization and urban planning culture, and its participation in international relations via the Great Silk Road are examined based on an analysis of written sources and historical archaeological data. The oasis's historical geographical the historical geographical boundaries of the oasis and the role of the natural landscape in its relations with neighboring regions are discussed.

Keywords: Shash, Ilok, Binkat, Banokat, Tashkent, Chirchik, Parak, Syr Darya, Chotkol, Koraama.

Introduction.

The article examines the participation of the Tashkent oasis, one of Central Asia's ancient historical-cultural regions, in regional and transregional economic and cultural relations during the early and medieval periods, and its influence on urbanization and cities in the oasis.

The issues of the Tashkent oasis's participation in regional and transregional economic and cultural relations in the early and medieval periods, and its impact on urbanization and the development of cities in the oasis, are examined based on an analysis of information from early medieval Chinese and Turkic written sources, and historical sources written in Arabic, Persian, Turkic, and other languages from the Islamic period.

Main part.

The routes of the medieval caravan roads of the Tashkent oasis had been fully established in antiquity. In the early Middle Ages, the historical processes that took place in Central Asia did not significantly affect the directions of the oasis's economic and cultural ties. The caravan routes that brought the Great Silk Road from the Fergana Valley to the Choch oasis via the Kamchik or Rozik passes in the Chotkal and Qurama mountains passed through cities and settlements in the Ohangaron and Chirchik river valleys. An analysis of the geographical location of the ancient cities in the Choch oasis reveals that they were situated near the oasis's water sources, and that the internal roads connecting them ran along the valleys of the Ohangaron and Chirchiq rivers. The roads connecting the oasis's cities with each other, as well as with villages, fields, pastures, and mines, formed an important link in the oasis's internal

trade route system and were connected to the system of transit routes linking the oasis with the Fergana Valley, Ustrushona, and Sogdiana. Specialists, noting that the oasis's ancient cities formed on the plains along the right bank of the Syr Darya and in the lower reaches of the Ohangaron and Chirchiq rivers, point out that neighboring Sogdiana had a significant influence on the start of the urbanization process in the oasis. This, in turn, indicates the close economic and cultural ties between these two historical and cultural provinces of Central Asia and the consistent operation of communication routes connecting the oasis with Sogdiana. During the period in question, the main road from the Tashkent oasis to Sogdiana. During the period in question, the main road from the oasis of Tashkent to Sogdiana ran through the northern regions of Ustrushona.

In the early Middle Ages, during the Ephthalites and the Turk Khaganate, relations with China reached a new level. This led to an increase in Central Asia's importance within the international communication network. It also calls for clarifying the participation of and role played by the oasis of Tashkent in the international economic and cultural relations conducted via the Great Silk Road. The cities located in the middle and lower basin of the Syr Darya also held great importance as transit areas in the operation of the transit trade routes connecting China with the Sasanian state and the Byzantine Empire through the territory of Central Asia. During the Turk Khaganate, which encompassed our region and the adjacent vast territories, significant profits were derived from foreign trade, prompting the establishment of customs posts along the trade routes to ensure the safety of caravan roads, The establishment of relevant infrastructure to ensure the security of caravan routes and to meet the essential needs of trade caravans (such as food and water, fodder for their animals, and other necessities) was initiated. All of this spurred the development of domestic and foreign economic and cultural relations.

In the early Middle Ages, trade routes that entered our region from China and Kashgar through the Tian Shan mountain passes led to the state of Parkan (Fergana) and Yettysu, The routes and fords running through the middle and lower reaches of the Syr Darya led to cities in the Amu Darya basin. In this system of international economic relations of the early Middle Ages, the importance of the Sogdian merchants, who operated under the patronage of the Turk Khaganate, grew even more. It is known that Sogdian merchants, in the early days of the Great Silk Road, began to establish their own trade offices ("trading factories") in the east, in the territories of Eastern Turkestan and Northern China. It should be noted that these trading posts, which were a vital link in Central Asia's economic trade relations with China, remained in existence until the 9th-10th centuries. Due to its geographical location, Central Asia was the

first region for the transportation of Chinese silk and porcelain to Southwest Asia and Europe, and thus it retained its important position in the international silk trade during the early Middle Ages.

In the 3rd–4th centuries AD, socio-economic changes began in the oasis of Tashkent that would prove significant for later periods. This was primarily related to the socio-political situation that emerged in the oasis after the collapse of the powerful Kanghu state. In the early Middle Ages, the Choch oasis also played a major role in the region's internal and external economic and cultural relations. During this period, there were 32 new cities in Choch, most of which were newly founded. Among them, the political importance of the city of Choch—located on the site of the Mingouric monument and replacing the crisis-stricken Qanka—began to grow. In Chinese sources of this period, the Choch oasis was called Shi, or Zhezhi and Zheshi, and Suye (Syr Darya – O.M.) river on its right bank, that its capital was the city of Zhesi, and that there was pearl stone in the mountains to its southeast. Routes ran through this oasis from the eastern (Fergana Valley) and northern steppe regions of the region toward the Amu Darya crossings, and the oasis was one of the key areas for contacts with the northern steppe nomads and China.

The oasis of Tashkent played an important role in the economic and cultural relations of the region's southern territories with the cities of Yettisu and Eastern Turkestan. In the developed Middle Ages, the Tashkent oasis was known as Shash and Ilok, with Ilok corresponding to the Angren River valley and Shash to the Parak River (Chirchik) valley. The oasis of Tashkent, one of the flourishing and important economic centers of Transoxiana, especially, Ilok was rich in precious minerals and was considered one of the main centers in Transoxiana for the extraction of various metallic and non-metallic ores during the period in question. Ibn Hawqal and Istakhri state that the Shash oasis is two days wide and three days long, and that its border on one side is the Shash (Syr Darya) river on one side, to the Iron Gate in the Kelif Desert between Shash and Isfijab on the second, to the Ilik Mountains on the third, and to Vinkerd, a Christian village, on the fourth.

The oasis is situated in a geographically favorable location, and in the 9th–10th centuries the main caravan routes passing through it were of transit and domestic importance. The road linking the oasis with Sogdiana ran in two directions. The first route, which passed through Jizzakh and the arid Mirzacho'l, led to the Christian village of Vinkerd, located at the crossing on the Chirchik River just downstream of its confluence with the Syr Darya. Caravans covered the distance from Jizzakh to this crossing in three days. Afterwards, the caravans traveled along

the left bank of the Chirchik River—past Chinokat, Shuturkat (Old Tashkent), and Zayatkent—toward Binkat. At the confluence of the Chirchik River with the Syr Darya, near present-day Chinos, the city of Chinokat played a key role in controlling the Syr Darya crossing, and some scholars interpret it as the “City of Chinese Merchants.” Binkat, the developed medieval capital of Shash, began to be called by a new name—Tashkent—from the 11th century. This city, with its citadel and fortress, stood out in the 9th-12th centuries not only as the administrative center of the oasis but also as one of the commercial and artisan centers of Mawara al-Nahr.

The second road connecting Sughd with Binkat, although long, was safe and heavily traveled. Sources call this road the “Banokat Road,” and it ran from Sogd through Jizzakh, Zomin, and Khavos. At Khavos, the road turned south and led to a ford just upstream of where the Ohangaron River flows into the Syr Darya. After crossing the Syr Darya, the route ran north along the river's right bank to Binkat, and from there it followed the left bank of the Ohangaron River to Harashkat and Khudaynakat. Here the Ohangaron was forded, and the road turned north into the Parak (Chirchik) valley, joining the Chinakkat–Binkat route at Shuturkat (Old Tashkent). Ibn Khordadbeh also provides information about the trade route from Samarkand to Shash via Zamin, noting that the distance was 42 farsakh. The oasis's internal roads were extensively networked, passing through all the major cities of Shash and Ilaq. Among them, the main routes were those connecting the city of Banokat on the Syr Darya with the capital of Shash, Binkat, and with the capital of Ilaq, the city of Tunkat. In the 9th-12th centuries, the city of Banokat was located on important routes leading from the Shash province to Ustrushona and Sogdiana. It was a major economic and cultural center located on the right bank of the Syr Darya, one farsakh downstream from where the Ilok (Angren) River flows into the Syr Darya.

During the period under review, the main internal routes of the oasis ran through its three major cities – Binkat (Tashkent), the capital of Shash; Tunkat, the capital of Ilaq; and Nukat (Ulkan Toytepa) located between them. The distance between Binkat and Tunkat was 10 farsakh, and the road connecting them passed through six other cities and numerous villages.

During the period in question, the cities of the Shash oasis were linked to Khujand and, through it, to the Fergana Valley. The road linking Shash's capital Tashkent with Khujand, a major city of Ustrushona, passed through the cities of Nuket (Tuytepa) and Biskat (Pskent). In the oasis's connections with the Fergana Valley, a route passing through the cities of Shavkat (Uvaytepa) and Ablig (Ablig) over the Kamchik and Rezakli mountain passes played a major role.

Conclusion.

In the early and developed Middle Ages, the oasis of Tashkent was one of the most economically advanced and culturally distinctive regions of Central Asia. The oasis's ancient cities were renowned as major centers of trade and cultural life in the region. The main agricultural sectors—irrigated agriculture, horticulture, and livestock farming—fully met domestic market demands, ensured food security in the oasis, and produced surplus goods for export. Mining, handicrafts, and trade were also highly developed in the oasis, and these processes spurred the development of caravan routes and infrastructure that served both internal and external connections.

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